

ONLINE SYSTEM: A MAGICAL STRATAGEM IN SCHOOL EDUCATION DURING COVID-19 CRISIS

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Cite This Article: Dr. Abantika Mondal & Sayanti Chakroborty, "Online System: A Magical Stratagem in School Education during Covid-19 Crisis", International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research in Arts and Humanities, Volume 6, Issue 2, Page Number 23-33, 2021.

Abstract:

During COVID19 pandemic situation online process has ployed the whole education system. It has become a stratagem in entire education field for almost two years. School going is a challenge to us. In India neo-normal kind of education system has been making itself as the best endeavor to cope up with this changed situation. It seems that online education system is a panacea to the world education, especially in any crisis. E-learning has many positive aspects. But we should remember it has so many negative facets also. In India school is not for the education it is also the way of survival of a child. Till now in a large part of India education is a luxury. Mid-day-meal is one of the vital schemes to bring children to school and prevent drop out, early marriage of girl child. COVID-19 situation is a big push to this situation. E-learning creates digital divide, it increases school dropout, child labor, early marriage of girl child, human trafficking, cyber crime in a threatening percentage. Online education within four walls creates psychological problems among students. Our paper deals with how online education effecting the holistic development of a child. Regarding this issue eleven dimensions were selected for the study. Opinions of students, teachers and parents are analyzed regarding this issue. Here we also try to find out the most effective dimensions, affecting the education system according to the opinion of students, teachers and parents. According to their opinion we also try to find out the solutions against the negative effects of online education.

Key Words: Online Education, Stratagem, Panacea, Holistic-Development, Digital Apartheid

Introduction:

Indian education system is one of the oldest systems of the world. The ancient glorious Indian education system followed the Gurukul or the Ashram system for education where pupils had to live in Ashram and had to complete their studies. There students mainly focused on Vedas, Puranas, Indian mythology, science, medical science, mathematics etc. under the direct supervision of their gurus (teachers). In India "guru-sishya" parampara is one of the sacred relations. According to Swamy Vivekananda, our education system should be man making education system. UNESCO says about Head-Heart-Hand coordination for holistic development of a child. According to UNESCO, the world stands in need of social systems renewal in a global age, and schools represent a key cultural institution that can shape new generations of young people to be forces for good in the world. No nation can afford to have a large number of its population to remain illiterate, ignorant and unskilled as these all cause poverty, superstitions and many other barriers in society.

Child rearing and the holistic development of a child is not a one-day magic. Education is the pillar of a society. Online education has become increasingly popular not only in India but also throughout the world for higher education, secondary education and also elementary education for more than one year, especially while the world has been suffering from Covid-19 pandemic. People are following the rules done by the governments of every countries to stay away from corona. Lock down is one of the major preventions to control the spread of novel corona virus. School education system is not out of this situation. In this hard circumstances' students are being enforced to study online without going to school.

Now is the era of E-learning system which is also called the online system or neo-normal system of education. A learning system based on formalized teaching but with the help of electronic resources is known as E-learning. While teaching is out of the classrooms and uses computers and the internet as major component. Online learning can also be termed as a network enabled transfer of skills and knowledge and the delivery of education (mainly informatics) is made to a large number of recipients at the same or different times.

Educational institutes closed due to Covid-19 Pandemic; the government has been encouraging online education to achieve academic continuity. Most high end private and public institutions have made the switch smoothly using online platforms such as Zoom, Google Classroom, Microsoft teams etc. While many still find it a herculean task. The challenges of online education are multifaceted. Our country is fighting against different kind of division among people regarding their family status, cast, religion, economic conditions etc. from the ancient era. But country is going to face a new class division by digital divide. Till now in a large part of India education is a luxury. Mid-day-meal is one of the vital schemes for bring children to school in India, children have to be brought to school by showing greed for food. Online education completely nullifies the distance

between students and teachers but creates a huge gap between student to student on the basis of inability to buy the facilities of online education. Doors of the schools are remaining closed from last of the March, 2020. Onset of online education, education system loses the human touch. Not only books, excellent study materials provide good education but human touch of a teacher can also change a student's life. Society suffers from increasing rate of school dropout, cybercrime, child labor, early marriage of girl child, child-abuse, human trafficking. Does away from the schools truly protect our country from pandemic or starts a new dark phase? Is online education for school students a magic stick of learning or a question mark for their survival? In our study we have tried to find out the answer of these questions. Major objectives of our study are

- To understand the effect of online teaching learning system upon the students of Upper Primary and Secondary level schools under West Bengal board.
- To determine the level of the adaptation of the new education system (online mode) by the parents or guardian.
- To understand how different dimensions related to online education, influence education and development of students or children.

Review of Literature:

Although online education is a new subject in India, a lot of research work has been done on it in the last year and it is still going on. From there we moved on to our current work with the help of some important ideas and works.

Access with Flexibility:

Prashanthi Karyala and Sarita Kamat did their research on "Online education in India -the bad and the ugly" (23rd September, 2020 in Policy, Teaching and Education). In Bangalore they have found that online classes are flexible, less stressful option, exploration of new methods of teaching and assessment. On the other hand, it was found that for the teachers it is problematic as a college teacher in suburban Mumbai expressed their view on it as body language and eye contact which are important cues for the teacher, are difficult to perceive in an online class. A parent of an 8 years old attending a private school in Gurgaon has the view of that little kids should not have the online class system as their concentration span is small and they do not pay attention after a while. The physical learning experience is much more valuable to them than the virtual one.

Socio-Economic Condition:

A school teacher from Ratnagiri Maharashtra has observed that in a class of 40 students, after two months of online classes, around 20 students regularly attend class with whatever device and connection they have. Around 5-8 students are completely absent till date and rest are fluctuating. It is an issue of socio-economic status. Live online classes are unavailable in maximum level as larger families cannot afford it. But it is also bad for the system where WhatsApp/You tube Videos are given to the students to acquire the online classes, it only encourages rote learning.

Difficulties for Girls:

There is also a problem faced by the girls as they have to do much household works than boys and it causes them not to attend the class on time. The other problem which is a notable hindrance for the girl student especially in upper primary level in lower middle class and often middle class families too that the girl child is not provided with the online classes where her brother is getting the same facility living in the same family. It is the cruel nature of gender biasness stereotyping that prevails still in our society even if the parent has that economic power.

Digital Divide:

Rinchen Norbu Wangchuk (26th June, 2020) has studied on the issue titled as "Classes online? What About Those Who share a Basic Phone Among a Family of 5?" and also "What About Places Where There is No Internet"-Despite a large base of internet users, the internet penetration rate in the country stands at just nearly 50% in 2020". According to him, India has massive user base, but Digital Divide remains though data is cheap compared to global prices the cost of internet-enabled devices remains as a barrier. Here is the major issue of having only one smartphone where the school going children in a family are three. The second concern is low bandwidth and recharge problems. In January 22, 2021 The Times of India published an interview of famous educationist Anita Rampal, former Dean, Faculty of Education, Delhi University. According to her digital education in this pandemic situation also contradicts the policy of Right to Education (RTE) Act.

Positive Attitude towards Online Education:

According to Ramesh Bijlani, a physician, philosopher and yoga teacher (6th February, 2021, The Speaking Tree, The Times of India), a change that has been relatively silent, but is likely to have a lasting and positive impact in the revolution in education. Formal education perhaps suffered, online classes notwithstanding. But non-formal education mushroomed at an unprecedented rate, widened its scope, improved in quality, and become accessible like never before. Most of the online courses, conferences, workshops and webinars are cost free or low cost. In short knowledge mostly became truly free and freely available; and the learners could pick and choose whatever they like. Still from a wider perspective, the 'new normal system' in education has added a one-world feeling. Overall, there is a very positive view regarding online system.

Negative Implication:

On the other hand, Educationist Anita Rampal, former Dean, Faculty of Education at Delhi University (22nd January, 2021, The Times of India), gave a quite different view and opinion regarding Online Classes. According to her digital education cannot substitute for real learning. Teachers are feeling trapped and enslaved to this disconcerting process that encourages coaching not teaching. In this process students only staring at a screen they do not think, question, argue, discuss but only act as remote receptors of what is beamed. According to her, students and their parents are forced to use gadgets to attend those classes even if they do not want. Online 'success' does not always show effective teaching-learning, because education cannot be transmitted through switch on and off button. Students must be provided meaningful academic curriculum alternatives.

National Surveys:

According to NCERT survey, one of three students find online classes difficult, (NCERT, Hindustan Times, New Delhi, 20th August, 2020) because of poor connectivity, disruption in electric supply and non-availability of devices, such as laptops and mobile phones. Students of Kendriya Vidyalaya Sanganathans, Navodaya Vidyalaya Samity and other Central Board of Secondary Education Schools participated in this survey. According to Dr. Surbhi Dayal faculty, Indian Institute of Management (IIM) Indore, 98% of students felt that quality of education has been compromised due to online format. Majority of the students reported that the online education system has hectic and frustrating. 75% reported that the excessive screen time hiked their mental stress (Times of India 5th February, 2021). The online survey conducted by the Learning Spiral showed that while children face issues in accessing education digitally, teacher face issues in delivering education through digital mediums. (13th April, 2021, Education, BW online Bureau) This same kind of issue was reported in India Today Web Desk, New Delhi 18th March, 2021.

Dark Side:

Unfortunately, a harsh reality with deep darkness comes when we came to know that the online education system promotes child marriage and trafficking during pandemic. Child marriage and sexual abuse have risen up to 52% in some states in India. Families have lost their livelihoods and particularly girl child has dropped out of school. Villages that haven't seen a single child marriage for several years, are now parents start to marrying their daughters in early age to reduce the number of mouths to feed. Childline, a children's helpline, reported that 17% increase in distress calls related to early marriage of girls in June and July this year (2020) compared to 2019 (BBC news of 18th September, 2020 Save the Children, 26th August 2021). Mamata Sardar, Youth advocate, Save the Children, West Bengal, said that girls in her village are increasingly being lured into marriage on social platform because of their addiction to social media due to online schooling. (Save the Children on 26th August, 2021).

Pedagogical Perspective:

Several researches reveal that e-learning has various fruitful effects on teaching learning process. Some pedagogical aspects e.g., constructive approach of learning, learning by doing, activity-based learning knowledge related to real life situation, virtual lab etc. are also flourishing through online teaching. From various aspects we cannot ignore advantages of technology but we cannot promote this digital apartheid. All the pedagogical aspects are also not covered by e-learning like value education, cooperative and collaborative learning, work and education, self-actualization, vocationalization of education and education for character building. According to famous educationist Anita Rampal, former Dean, Faculty of Education, Delhi University, digital education day by day has been becoming a part of IT business, it cannot promote the overall development of a child. She told that digital education or education provided by IT industry cannot be the substitute of a teacher. A Holistic development of child is not possible only by online learning. For changed situation it works as support system but cannot be the overall system (The Times of India, January 22, 2021)

Materials and Methods:

Survey Area: Rural and Urban areas in West Bengal

Demographic Variables: Students, teachers, parents from govt., govt. aided and Private schools under West Bengal Board.

Dependent Variables: Online Education

Independent Variables: 11 Dimensions Act as 11 Independent Variables

Basis of Selecting the Variables:

Upper primary and Secondary level students from West Bengal Board are selected because these students are the major part of the school education system. End of secondary level students face their first board examination (Madhyamik examination) of their life. So, this section of students and their study both are very vital.

Construction of Test:

- 3 separate feedback form (regarding online education) has been developed one for students, one for teachers and another one for parents.
- Reliability and Validity of the feedback form tested by authentic person of this field.

- Feedback form is developed on the basis of 11 dimensions and Google form has been created differently for students, parents, teachers. These forms are circulated to the concern person through email and what's app.

The Dimensions are Following:

- Dimension regarding technological facility (V1)
- Dimension regarding proper use of technology (V2)
- Dimension regarding usability and effectiveness of online education (V3)
- Dimension regarding evaluation through online (V4)
- Dimension regarding character building and holistic development of a child (V5)
- Dimension regarding malpractices in online mode of education (V6)
- Dimension regarding effect of online education on society (V7)
- Dimension regarding interest and motivation towards online education (V8)
- Dimension regarding the relationship between socioeconomic condition and online education (V9)
- Dimension regarding effect of online education on social isolation (V10)
- Dimension regarding effect of online education and govt. polices and support (V11)

Selection of Scale:

Likert's 3-Point Scale: Parameters are Agree, Sometimes, Disagree

Result:

For this study we have divided online education system into eleven (11) dimensions. We have collected the views of different stakeholders on different dimensions of online education system. These stakeholders are directly and indirectly related with online education system. These stakeholders act as sample for our study. Here for the study we divided these stakeholders into three (3) categories (Students, Teachers and Parents).

Views of the stakeholders on different dimensions are collected through statement form. For this COVID-19 situation (Lockdown condition) schools are remaining closed from last of March, 2020 to till date.

Table 1: Table represents the views (in %) of Students, Teachers and Parents regarding the different dimension of online education system

S.No	Dimensions	Students View (In percentage)			Teachers View (In percentage)			Parents View (In percentage)		
		A	MG	DA	A	MG	DA	A	MG	DA
1	Dimension regarding technological facility	69.25	17.45	13.2	50	29.5	20.5	33.77	26.95	42.3
2	Dimension regarding proper use of technology	65.20	20.73	14.07	64.6	21.54	10.76	38.45	38.5	23.1
3	Dimension regarding usability and effectiveness of online education	33.96	42.76	23.76	41.35	31.72	26.92	40.80	28.40	30.8
4	Dimension regarding evaluation through online	43.4	17	39.6	7.7	15.4	76.9	23.1	23.1	53.8
5	Dimension regarding character building and holistic development of a child	46.35	19.82	33.85	21.9	42.47	35.57	39.65	40.1	20.27
6	Dimension regarding malpractices in online mode of education	59.4	20.75	19.85	52.56	41.03	6.4	43.33	27.2	29.5
7	Dimension regarding negative effect of online education on society	55.96	24.53	19.5	51.92	29.8	18.25	53.8	30.8	15.4
8	Dimension regarding interest and motivation towards online education	54.4	15.1	30.18	26.9	25.95	40.37	40.9	30.93	28.23
9	Dimension regarding the relationship between socio economic condition and online education	54.7	26.4	18.9	84.6	11.5	3.8	46.2	23.1	30.8
10	Dimension regarding effect of online education on social isolation	44.47	40.41	15.07	93.6	6.4	0	94.86	5.13	0
11	Dimension regarding	61.35	11.8	26.87	55.13	19.23	19.23	26.9	46.15	26.95

effect of online education and govt. polices and support									
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Note: A for AGREE, MG for MODERATE, DA for DISAGREE

Table 1 shows the total percentage of opinion of students, teachers and parents. from this table we get a comparative idea about the opinions of three different categories of people (students, teachers and parents).

Table 2: Table of correlation of dependent variable (Online education system) with different independent variables(According to parents' view).

Rank Order of Correlation	Total	Total	V1	V2	V3	V4
		1				
8	V1	0.4699	1			
4	V2	0.5978	0.1274	1		
1	V3	0.8823	0.3598	0.6891	1	
6	V4	0.5188	0.0468	0.3060	0.5827	1
5	V5	0.5526	-0.1581	0.3707	0.4977	0.6664
3	V6	0.6362	0.0123	0.3465	0.4173	0.2630
9	V7	0.4462	0.4152	-0.0860	0.1222	0.0218
2	V8	0.7070	0.3362	0.3696	0.7853	0.3125
10	V9	0.3014	0.1203	-0.1492	0.0433	-0.1262
7	V10	0.5182	0.5170	0.2591	0.3875	0.0692
11	V11	0.3008	0.0570	0.0631	0.2564	-0.1068

V5	V6	V7	V8	V9	V10	V11
1						
0.2259	1					
0.0859	0.2791	1				
0.1951	0.3159	0.2144	1			
0.0964	0.5215	0.1046	0.0853	1		
0.1881	0.1759	0.1911	0.5133	0.1777	1	
0.1803	0.1685	0.4425	0	0.1097	-0.281	1

According to Table 2, V3 (usability and effectiveness of online education) and V8 (interest and motivation towards online education) are highly correlated with online education system. V3 is more than 88% and V8 is more than 70% correlated with online education system. So, from the table we can say that according to parents' opinion usability and effectiveness of online education, interest and motivation towards online education are two major factors among all the eleven factors affect the online education system.

Table 3: Stepwise Regression Analysis for V3 and V8

Regression Statistics					
Multiple R	0.960757				
R Square	0.923054				
Adjusted R Square	0.907664				
Standard Error	1.041323				
Observations	13				
Anova					
	Df	SS	MS	F	Significance F
Regression	2	130.0795	65.03977	59.98026676	2.6974E-06
Residual	10	10.84353	1.084353		
Total	12	140.9231			
	Coefficients	Standard Error	t Stat	P-value	
Intercept	1.947	1.435	1.357	0.205	
V3	2.138	0.310	6.904	0.000	
V8	0.986	0.204	4.847	0.001	

According to regression analysis V3 (p value .000) and V6 (p value.001) are highly significant to affect the online education system and according to regression statistic contribution of both the factors to effect online education is 92%.

Table 4: Stepwise regression analysis for V3 and V8

Regression Statistics	
Multiple R	0.861574
R Square	0.742309
Adjusted R Square	0.718883
Standard Error	1.816956
Observations	13

Anova	Df	SS	MS	F	Significance F
Regression	1	104.6085	104.6085	31.68679	0.000154
Residual	11	36.31461	3.301328		
Total	12	140.9231			
	Coefficients	Standard Error	t Stat	P-value	
Intercept	6.292135	1.954645	3.219067	0.008173	
V3	2.764045	0.491028	5.629102	0.000154	

According (Table.4) to regression analysis V3 (p value .000154) is highly significant to affect the online education system and according to regression statistic contribution of this factor to effect online education is 74%. Among all the eleven factors.

Table 5: Table of correlation of dependent variable (Online education system) with different independent variables (According to teachers view)

Correlation Rank Order		Total	V1	V2	V3	V4
	Total	1				
5	V1	0.4768	1			
3	V2	0.6567	0.4588	1		
1	V3	0.7932	0.3866	0.4478	1	
4	V4	0.5238	0.1666	0.3164	0.4003	1
2	V5	0.6644	0.2134	0.2402	0.7127	0.5645
10	V6	-0.137	-0.0133	-0.4025	-0.3412	-0.1814
7	V7	0.4312	-0.2090	-0.0314	0.1780	0.1649
6	V8	0.4448	-0.0442	0.2432	0.2339	0.1797
11	V9	-0.0839	-0.0498	-0.2962	-0.0046	0.2027
9	V10	-0.1812	-0.1895	-0.0683	-0.3187	-0.4559
8	V11	0.3557	0.1540	0.1266	0.2430	0.0279

V5	V6	V7	V8	V9	V10	V11
1						
0.0445	1					
0.2210	0.3790	1				
-0.0053	-0.4759	0.2912	1			
-0.106	-0.0798	-0.1080	0.0627	1		
-0.1694	0.2829	-0.1283	-0.2360	-0.1235	1	
0.0978	-0.0314	0.0997	0.0536	-0.0562	0.1689	1

According (Table 5) to teachers V3 (usability and effectiveness of online education), V5 (Dimension regarding character building and holistic development of a child), V2 (Dimension regarding proper use of technology) and V4 (Dimension regarding evaluation through online) are highly correlated with online education system. V3 is more than 79%, V5 66%, V2 65% and V4 52% correlated with online education system. So, from the table we can say that according to teachers' opinion usability and effectiveness of online education, Dimension regarding character building and holistic development of a child, Dimension regarding proper use of technology are three major factors among all the eleven factors affect the online education system.

Table 6: Stepwise Regression Analysis for V2, V3, V4 and V5

Regression Statistics					
Multiple R	0.886834				
R Square	0.786474				
Adjusted R Square	0.745803				
Standard Error	3.288992				
Observations	26				
Anova					
	Df	SS	MS	F	Significance F
Regression	4	836.7178	209.1795	19.33719	8.43E-07
Residual	21	227.1668	10.81747		
Total	25	1063.885			

	Coefficients	Standard Error	t Stat	P-value
Intercept	46.12238	5.152841	8.950865	1.3E-08
V2	1.044884	0.326424	3.201007	0.004293
V3	1.429461	0.515207	2.774536	0.011359
V4	1.266091	1.332042	0.950489	0.352676
V5	0.873011	0.738215	1.182596	0.250186

According (Table 6) to regression analysis V2 (p value .004) and V3 (p value.012) are highly significant to affect the online education system and according to regression statistic contribution of V2, V3, V4 and V5 are the factors to effect online education is 78%.

Table 7: table of correlation of dependent variable (Online education system) with different independent variables (According to students view)

Correlation Rank Order		Total	V1	V2	V3	V4
	Total	1				
10	V1	0.5157	1			
2	V2	0.8403	0.5651	1		
5	V3	0.7272	0.5509	0.7300	1	
7	V4	0.7013	0.3637	0.5776	0.6032	1
3	V5	0.8314	0.4045	0.6054	0.6334	0.5902
8	V6	0.7036	0.0697	0.4574	0.2157	0.4388
4	V7	0.7545	0.0716	0.5212	0.3623	0.6528
1	V8	0.9015	0.4881	0.7406	0.7015	0.7886
9	V9	0.7023	0.3970	0.5949	0.4966	0.6724
11	V10	0.0901	-0.0776	0.0223	-0.1379	-0.4652
6	V11	0.7126	0.1140	0.4844	0.3330	0.5541

V5	V6	V7	V8	V9	V10	V11
1						
0.5796	1					
0.5919	0.6722	1				
0.7807	0.5648	0.7181	1			
0.6213	0.4233	0.5700	0.7236	1		
-0.0578	0.1971	-0.0620	-0.2648	-0.2292	1	
0.5125	0.6721	0.6872	0.5931	0.4197	0.1068	1

According to Table 7 (students view) V8 (Dimension regarding interest and motivation towards online education), V5 (Dimension regarding character building and holistic development of a child), V2 (Dimension regarding proper use of technology) are highly correlated with online education system. V8 is more than 90%, V2 84%, V5 83% correlated with online education system. This table shows the correlation rank order. From here we can say that V3 and V7 are also correlated with online education system. So, from the table we can say that according to teachers' opinion usability and effectiveness of online education, Dimension regarding Dimension regarding interest and motivation towards online education, character building and holistic

development of a child), proper use of technology are three major factors among all the eleven factors affect the online education system.

Table 8: Stepwise Regression Analysis for V2, V5 and V8

Regression Statistics					
Multiple R	0.956051				
R Square	0.914033				
Adjusted R Square	0.90877				
Standard Error	4.382384				
Observations	53				
ANOVA	Df	SS	MS	F	Significance F
Regression	3	10005.73	3335.244	173.6628	4.23E-26
Residual	49	941.059	19.20529		
Total	52	10946.79			
	Coefficients	Standard Error	t Stat	P-value	
Intercept	28.46148	2.905615	9.795336	3.98E-13	
V2	2.614509	0.448339	5.831542	4.25E-07	
V5	2.225401	0.496029	4.486434	4.39E-05	
V8	1.246544	0.250186	4.98247	8.22E-06	
V7	2.896607	0.518601	4.698626	4.89E-05	

According to regression analysis V2 (p value 4.25E-07) and V5 (p value 4.39E-05) and V8 (8.22E-06) are highly significant to affect the online education system and according to regression statistic contribution of V2, V5 and V8 are the factors to effect online education is 91%.

From the statistical analysis independent variables (Dimensions) regarding proper use of technology (V2), Dimension regarding usability and effectiveness of online education (V3), Dimension regarding evaluation through online (V4), Dimension regarding character building and holistic development of a child (V5), Dimension regarding interest and motivation towards online education (V8) play major role in online education system (neo normal education system). According to the view of students and teachers V2 and V5 effecting online education, parents and teachers both said that V3 is one of the major factors and parents and students both told that V8 is one of the major factors for effecting online education.

So according to the study there is no significant correlation between technological facility (V1) and online education system, malpractices done by the students (V6) and online education system, no significant correlation between socio-economic condition (V9) and online education system, social isolation (V10) and online education. There is no significant correlation between govt. policies (V11) as well as support and online education system. We found that this opinions or views are same according to students, teachers and parents.

According to the study there is no significant difference among the opinions and views of the Students, Teachers and Parents regarding online education system is rejected. in the sense there is difference in the opinion of students, teachers and parents, factors effecting the online education system. Because according to the view of students and teachers V2 and V5 effecting online education, parents and teachers both said that V3 is one of the major factors and parents and students both told that V8 is one of the major factors for effecting online education. So, students think V8, V5, V2 are major factors, teachers think V2, V3, V4, and V5 are major factors and parents think V3 and V8 are the major factors effecting online education.

We did not find any significant relationship with socio economic condition and online education. Because now a day's android mobile set is easily available or accessible to the any group of socio-economic condition s. Now a day's govt. is also funding school students for online education in regard of purchasing tab or android mobile free of cost. So, socio economic condition here is not a major factor for effecting online education system. Though from descriptive statistical analysis we get a view socio economic condition effects online education. Lower socio-economic condition group facing difficulties regarding online education. But statistically we did not (Pearson coefficient) get any significant relation socio economic condition with online education. Because usability and accessibility of android mobile set acts as cartoon on the real situation. So, we need to raise the cartoon to realise the actual situation.

But from the study a vital finding we got that students told that online education system has remarkable negative effect on society (V7) it promotes digital divide among students. But according to statistical data we did not get any significant relation but from correlation study it is 75% correlated with online education system. Here students reveal a vital side of online education system.

Discussion:

According to the study how different dimensions effect online education are discussed here with reference to the result

Technological facility: 69.25 % students, 50% teachers and 33.77% parents (Table: 1) agree with the online mode of education as good as they don't face any problem regarding any kind of technological issues or

its accessibility while doing online classes. A positive correlation (student and teacher views) between the technological facility and online education system was noticed. Because android phones and net connection are easily available to every student.

Proper use of technology: Maximum students and teachers told that they are using the technology properly. But near about 38% parents said that students are not properly following the decorum in doing online classes. In online classes students and teachers are participating directly, parents act as observer for their child (students). Because parents can watch students directly but teachers are unable to do so. Due to this, e-learning created a gap between teacher and student. In the long run it will affect students' holistic development.

Usability and effectiveness of online education: Online education creates a "one-world feeling" regarding information gathering and teaching-learning process. Though students told that often they are not able to understand chapters properly. They have also dissatisfaction about doubt clearing. 33.96% students, 41.35% teachers agree that they properly use the online class system where as 23.76% students disagree with the same point as they unable to follow the system properly. On the other hand, parents of 40.80% agree that their children use it properly. Although, it is to be mentioned that teachers want some refreshment course for them to enhance their capability and make themselves more updated in this issue as there is lack of it. The parents too are facing problems in this respect as many students are seeking helps from their parents to understand their lessons but parents have no such time or that much of knowledge to make understand the lesson.

Evaluation through online: 43.4% students, 7.7% teachers think that proper evaluation can be made through online mode. 17% students, 15.4% teachers and 23.1% parents don't know if evaluation through online is good or bad. Again, parents also don't know what is right or wrong too. But interestingly, maximum teachers (76.9%) and parents disagree with online evaluation process. Almost nobody is satisfied with this process. But students (43.4%) are not so much aware of this. Both teachers and parents have shown their negative attitude toward it. They think this method promotes some malpractices regarding examination and there remains a lack for proper judgment.

Character building and holistic development of a child: 46.35% students agreed that they are going through overall development. On the other hand, only 21.9% teachers and 39.65% parents told that there is scope of character building and holistic development for the students through this system. Most of the teachers (35.57%) and parents are thinking that children are not developing holistically. Whereas most of the students keep the opposite view regarding this issue because they think that they are able to secure very high marks in the examinations, getting worldwide connectivity and gather huge information. Both parents and teachers are complaining about the lack of physical fitness and moral values among students. Many new diseases are taking shelter in the bodies of teachers and students. Mental peace has gone, according to them. Thus, there is a strong correlation (mainly according to teachers view-66%) between character building and holistic development of the child and online mode of education.

Malpractices in online mode of education: 59.4 % students, 52.56% teachers and 43.33 % parents agree that there is a huge scope of malpractices through online mode of education. Face book, Twitter, Online games, Online chatting, Instagram, you tube are the common areas and apps in our mobile phone today. Students are also introducing themselves in these apps. But the bad thing is that they are getting addicted towards it. Students, teachers and parents everybody in majority of the same opinion that online education system has given the scope to the students in malpractice in the name of study the lessons. Students are forcing their parents to give the phone and searching other apps behind it. Thus, online education system in this respect has a great negative impact upon students. So, there is a negative correlation between malpractices and online education system.

Effect of online education on society: More than 50% parents, students and teachers told that there is a negative effect of online education on society. According to the view of students' negative effect on society has shown 75% correlation with online education. There is a great question of digital apartheid that means online education system is creating distinction among the people who are digitally privileged and who are not. Now-a-days almost everyone has smart phone but regarding net connection and it's charge it is a problem for many. Thus, it can be said that those who have the smart phone will progress in life, if they do not have it then they will regress. On the other hand, many parents have negative approach towards the system. If there is a question of communication among students, they use social media, last of all which becomes a habit. Sometimes it indulges some crime too. Again, regarding this, teachers have faced many problems in taking classes from home because household works disturb their teaching-learning or professional work. So, there is a negative correlation between online education system and its effect on society.

Interest and motivation towards online education: The result shows that students (54.4%) are mostly telling that they have interest and are motivated by the online education system. 40.9% parents kept same views. They are interested to do more online education for future study and employment. In this regard in positive sense teacher percentage is 26.9%. Now it must be clarified that from which angle they are feeling interested. Students are getting a chance to handle the mobile phone in the name of study and they fulfill their queries with the help of different search engines. Many parents thought (70% correlation), students get lots of information

and different kinds of online study materials within their home. Parents thought students are learning a lot. On the other hand, teachers' thought completely contradicts to students' thought. They don't think this system can motivate the students for learning because students only gather huge amount of data and information but do not learn. Thus, interest and motivation are correlated negatively with online education according to teachers view.

Relationship between socio economic condition and online education: Highest percentage of teachers (84.6%) have said that there is the great effect of financial condition of the family on online education. They think the students are facing difficulties to avail the online classes due to lack of enough financial support from the family. Regarding this view parents are less in number (46.2%) than students (54.7%). Thus, there is definitely a negative relation between socio economic condition and online education. But according to statistical analysis there is no significant relation with socio economic condition and online education. Because now-a-days android mobile set is easily available or accessible to any group of socio-economic condition and govt. also give school students tab or android mobile free of cost. So socio-economic condition here is not a major factor for effecting online education system.

Effect of online education on social isolation: In case of social isolation 44.47% students, 93.6% teachers and 94.86% parents agreed that today's online education is responsible for social isolation mainly because of de-schooling.

Effect of online education and govt. polices and support: From parents' point of view it is clear that they are not satisfied with the whole system conducted by the government through only passing some polices regarding the issue of online classes. Govt. should be more concerned about it as it is the question of the future of the students and majority of the parents are unable to provide facility to their children. Though in that case, students and teachers are showing their satisfaction on governmental steps taken for the online class system onwards. Perhaps students cannot understand properly of this issue but from teachers' point of view they are little bit of worries how they can be satisfied enough with this issue as majority of them have supported it though they are fully aware of the effect of socio-economic condition upon online class.

On the other hand, the Madhyamik Pariksha or the 10th class board examination is vital for a students' life as they first time face the board examination. Many students are of opinion that they don't want to give it where majority of the students understand the value of it and support in giving the examination. But the assessment system is worthy to be mentioned here. Students are of opinion that if there is no possibility of taking offline mode of the exam, it could be online or assignment system to evaluate the candidate properly. Teachers and parents are also thinking so. Thus, it can be said that this major issue should be of more concern for the authority, if again this same situation arrives and students cannot go for offline examination. There should be a way out of it, which will lead them in future progress.

Yet the online education system also indicates a way towards dark alley. During this pandemic situation online education creates a digital divide among students. It is a matter of concern too that the proper use of online system of study has an immense effect on the lives of girl children especially. As it is observed that girls are being exploited on social media as children spend more time online during the pandemic with a spike in child marriages making them vulnerable to traffickers. The dropout rate has increased and the child labour too has grown to its full. It has caused death to the teenagers in a high rate during this pandemic situation. The mental health has been highly affected during this situation which has led the children to abnormal behaviour. Now a day's students are associated with so much search engines for various purposes. But school, teachers and school friends are not the synonyms of such kind of search engine. They are the major pillars of the man making education. So, for the sustainable development of a human civilization school education system should be immediately run by blended approach (combination of online education process with traditional place-based classroom methods)

Recommendations:

- Online process should be integral part (like Blended approach or hybrid classroom) of education system for holistic development of a child.
- Orientation programme regarding e-learning management system should be arranged for teachers in conducting online classes properly.
- In school ICT must be a major subject like others. So there need a change in curriculum.
- There should be awareness programs regarding use of internet for students, teacher and parents in regular interval.

Conclusion:

E-learning will have been keeping a footprint on education system globally during this pandemic with its positive and negative impact. It is up to human being how they utilize it so, as of online education system. It causes health issues, social isolation which leading to mental and psychological issues. The socially backward class people are facing the major problems because of their financial instability. Except all of these issues online system of study has marked itself as the priority of a student life. So, to make it easy for the students govt. should take much responsibilities, teachers must update themselves more to teach their students and in courageous ways. Not only that, the technological facilities must be available to all. For the progress of

civilization holistic development of the students is necessary. For this blended approach (Online and offline-traditional education system) should be the best way to fight any difficult situation. Last of all we can conclude that online education may be a major support for the education system but not the overall.

Acknowledgement:

Authors want to express thanks to the teachers and students and the parents of the students for their active participation during the course of the survey. Authors are also again thankful to Department of Teacher Education, WBUTTEPA, West Bengal, India for their kind co-operation to do this study.

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